

TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL ANALYSES, MAGNETIC MOMENTS AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA FOR Cu(II) COMPLEXES

Ligand No.	Empirical formula of the complex Cu(SB)H ₂ O	% Cu	% N	ω_{eff} (300°K) B.M.	Electronic spectra ^b λ_{max} (nm)
Ia	(C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂)Cu.H ₂ O	20.01 (20.19) ^a	13.28 (13.36)	0.83	390, 570, 625(sh)
Ib	(C ₈ H ₉ ON ₂)Cu.H ₂ O	23.20 (23.28)	25.55 (25.64)	1.34	390, 550, 630(sh)
Ic	(C ₇ H ₈ O ₂ N ₂)Cu.H ₂ O	24.40 (24.31)	21.60 (21.42)	1.02	390, 570

^a. Values in parentheses are the calculated values.

^b. Electronic Spectra in Nujol.

present Cu(II) complexes may be due to ligand → metal charge transfer^{6,7}. The three infra-red bands of all the Schiff bases observed between 925 and 1020 cm⁻¹ (assigned to NO frequencies of the oxime group) are shifted to higher frequencies (viz. between 970 and 1190 cm⁻¹) in the Cu(II) chelates indicating that the oxime nitrogen is a potential bonding site in all the complexes^{8,9}. The i.r. band due to C=N grouping (including the oxamino group) located at 1600 and 1650 cm⁻¹ in the Schiff bases Ia and Ib respectively are shifted to lower frequency region (by 10-20 cm⁻¹) in the corresponding Cu(II) complexes showing the involvement of the azomethine nitrogen in bonding^{9,10}. The broad band at 1670 cm⁻¹ in Ic assigned to the C=N stretching frequency coupled with the amide grouping, disappeared in the Cu(II) complex with the appearance of new weak-band at 1610 cm⁻¹ suggesting that bonding has taken place through the amide group via enolisation and through the azomethine nitrogen at the same time⁹⁻¹². In Ia, the strong broad band in the 3 μ region assigned to ν (OH) of both oxime group and salicyl residue, is shifted to much lower frequency region (by about 300 cm⁻¹) in its Cu(II) complex suggesting involvement of both phenolic-OH (of salicyl residue) and oxime group (after deprotonation) in complexation⁹⁻¹². The broad strong bands at 3400 and 3360 cm⁻¹ observed respectively in Ib and Ic may be assigned to OH stretching frequency of the NOH group; this band either disappeared or became very weak in their Cu(II) complexes suggesting deprotonation and involvement of the oxime group in complex formation as advocated above. It appears, therefore, that all the three Schiff base molecules containing oxime grouping exhibit diacidic tridentate function in complex formation with Cu(II) giving polynuclear species.

The cryomagnetic studies on these Cu(II) chelates are in progress and details will be communicated in due course.

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Titrimetric Determination of Amines via Formation of 2,4-Dinitrobenzenesulphenamides

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ALIPHATIC amines can be determined with ease by acidimetric titrations, however, satisfactory acidimetric titrations of aromatic amines were impossible for a long time because the basicity of water and that of lower alcohols is too high. Visual or potentiometric determination of these bases in organic solvents with perchloric acid represented a great advance¹; however, those amines which contain negative substituents cannot be titrated². The bromination method does not enjoy wide popularity because there are so many interferences owing to the oxidizing and substitution properties of

bromine. Van Slyke method for the determination of aliphatic amines generally gives low results³. Determination of amines by titration of their picrates, though accurate, is tedious⁴. The development of a titrimetric procedure based on the quantitative reaction of 2,4-dinitrobenzenesulphenyl chloride with certain amines was, therefore, undertaken. The reaction is sufficiently rapid and accurate. An amine is warmed with an excess of 2,4-dinitrobenzenesulphenyl chloride, the unreacted sulphenyl chloride is titrated against sodium methoxide using thymol blue as indicator. The end point is stable for five minutes. The results obtained with some of the available amines are recorded in Table 1. Amines with ortho substituents and those rendered less basic due to negative substituents do not react quantitatively.

TABLE 1—TITRIMETRIC DETERMINATION OF AMINES

Amine	Wt. Range mg.	Average ^a % purity	Standard deviation
Aniline ^b	60–100	99.96	0.0381
N-Methylaniline	60–100	99.95	0.0058
<i>p</i> -Toluidine	50–75	98.17	0.1466
<i>m</i> -Toluidine	50–100	99.96	0.3007
<i>p</i> -Anisidine	60–80	99.13	0.0667
<i>p</i> -Phenetidine	50–90	99.71	0.0710
<i>p</i> -Chloroaniline	50–90	99.64	0.0738
Sulphanilic acid ^c	60–100	99.59	0.0418
Ethanol amine	40–80	99.89	0.0557

^a. Average of three readings.

^b. G. R., Sarabhai M. Chemicals.

^c. A.R., B.D.H.

Procedure:

2,4-Dinitrobenzenesulphenyl chloride (200 to 300 mg) prepared and purified according to the reported procedure⁵, is dissolved in 10 ml of ethylene chloride in a titration flask, followed by the addition of a weighed quantity of an amine (50 to 100 mg). Lithium carbonate (1 g) is added and the contents are swirled for half an hour at 40–50°. After cooling to room temperature, thymol blue (2 drops, 0.3% W/V, in methanol) is introduced and the solution is titrated against 0.1N sodium methoxide to a distinct brown colour.

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Synthesis of Some New Indole Derivatives

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WE have earlier reported the amoebicidal and cysticidal activity of the compounds having amino acid esters linked to the carboxylic group of substituted indole 3-acetic acids via an amidic linkage¹. It is of interest to substitute an aryl group in place of alkyl chain of amino acids and explore the possibility of increase of lipid solubility. Accordingly, a series of compounds having substituted *p*-aminobenzoates and salicylates linked to the carboxyl group of indole 3-acetic and -propionic acids were synthesized and tested for amoebicidal activity.

The compounds(I) were synthesized by the following scheme

Dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (2 g, 0.01 mole) in methylene chloride (30 c.c.) was added to a solution of alkyl *p*-amino benzoate or salicylate (0.01 mole) and substituted indole 3-alkanoic acid (0.011 mole) in methylene chloride (20 ml) with cooling. After stirring for 10 hrs. at room temperature, the precipitated dicyclohexyl urea was filtered off, the solution washed successively with 20 ml. portions of *N* HCl, *N* potassium carbonate and

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